

Determinants of Professional Orientation of Future Psychologists on Correctional Support of Children with Psychophysical Disorders

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Abstract: *This article is devoted to highlighting theoretical and methodological foundations of the study of professional orientation of future special psychologists on correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders. On the basis of the structural components of professional orientation of special psychologists developed by us, the main determinants of professional orientation of future specialists on correctional support of children with psychophysical developmental disorders were determined, specifically: in the study of the motivational-target component of professional orientation of the future specialists in the field of special psychology, we focused on the study of the dominant motives for choosing a profession; on formation of a humanistic orientation; on the meaningful life orientations of the individual; exploring the emotional and gnostic component of the professional orientation of future psychologists for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, represented by sensory and informational structures, we paid attention to formation and objectivity of understanding future professional activities, its requirements for the personality of a specialist; on the attitude to the future profession and to the process of mastering it; identification with the subjects of future professional activity; to the level of development of empathy, altruism, attraction and congruence; the regulatory component of the professional orientation of future special psychologists on correctional support of children with psychophysical disorders was studied taking into account the level of maturity of professional self-esteem and professional prognosis.*

Keywords: *Components of orientation, training program, special psychologist, humanistic approach, professional interest, empathy, professional identity.*

How to cite: Afuzova, H., Ogorodniychuk, Z., Pavelkiv, V., Mamicheva, O., Prokofieva, O., & Androsovyh, K. (2022). Determinants of Professional Orientation of Future Psychologists on Correctional Support of Children with Psychophysical Disorders. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 13(1Sup1), 188-206. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/13.1Sup1/312>

Introduction

The system of psycho-correctional support for children with mental disorders is in its initial stage of development. The content of education of psychologists involves fundamental psychological training, but a strong theoretical basis is supported by fragmentary psychological practice, which is represented only by the main types of professional activities – psychodiagnostics and psychocorrection. This does not take into account the fact that the specifics of each professional activity lies in its inherent terminology, specific ways of action and behavior (Huidu, 2020), a peculiar nature of the activities of participants in the process, special internal states of the subjects of interaction. As a result, there is a practical and personal unpreparedness of graduates for implementation of appropriate psycho-correctional support for children with mental and physical disorders. There is an issue of special professional training, formation and development of certain professionally oriented personal qualities that would ensure the full value of this type of psycho-correctional care.

Based on the theoretical analysis of scientific sources (Arkes & Garske, 1982; Sheremet et al., 2019), we concluded that it is necessary to clearly define the specifics of professional activities of a special psychologist, especially recognizing the need for qualified correctional support during inclusion of this group of children in the environment of peers with normal level of development.

In the course of work, teachers, students and parents turn to a practical psychologist in case of developmental problems, difficulties in learning and relationships. The focus of the practical psychologist's attention was gradually shifted towards predicting and preventing such difficulties, which in turn required radical changes in the professional activities of school practical psychologists. At the same time, similar tasks, but with the category of more complex cases (“abnormal”, “defective” children), were solved by defectology and related sciences, which studied both significant developmental disorders of children (mental retardation, blindness, deafness, etc.) and less pronounced (mental retardation, developmental disorders with minimal brain dysfunction, erased developmental disorders, etc.). Thus, children of some categories fell under the study of both practical psychology and defectology, which served to optimize care for such children, taking into account the experience of interacting sciences, which was supplemented by mutual enrichment of theory and practice.

As a result of expanding contacts with developed Western countries, the worldview of society shows global changes, including in the perception

and attitude of people with mental and physical disorders: the ideas of human rights, social responsibility, humanization of society, etc. were increasingly proclaimed. Domestic researchers had had the opportunity to get acquainted with the experience and research of foreign colleagues in the field of education, which in accordance with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child highlights the concept of co-education of children with disabilities and children who develop normally. In the current social situation, the changes primarily affected the educational system (both general and special), which, in turn, expanded the requirements for professionals involved in the problems of development, education and upbringing of children. All this contributed to increasing attention to psychological knowledge about children with mental and physical disorders.

The pedagogical higher educational establishments of the country are faced with the need to train specialists who comprehend the system of psychological knowledge about children with atypical development, understand their difficulties, know peculiarities of their education and life activities. The academic discipline “Special Psychology” was included in the curricula of state standards as a mandatory discipline of vocational education. The specialization of a psychologist, whose professional activity is related to children with psychophysical disorders, received a similar name (Fedorishin, 1988).

A specialist who specializes as a special psychologist must be trained to work with children and adults with mental and physical disorders, including the following: mental; of cognitive development; of hearing and sight; of musculoskeletal system; of speech; emotional disorders, including early child autism; behaviour and activities, as well as with severe complex disorders. Also, a special psychologist must be able to work with family members of individuals with mental and physical disorders; with teachers and social workers who provide training, rehabilitation and social support to the specified contingent.

Psychological features of professional orientation of future psychologists on the correctional support

Studying the experience of training psychological personnel and program documents of other post-Soviet countries, we came to the conclusion that the training program for a special psychologist should include:

- knowledge of general psychological, psychophysiological, clinical and psychological principles of study and correction of abnormalities in the

mental development of children, taking into account their individual and age characteristics;

- mastering the methodological, theoretical and applied aspects of prevention and correction of disorders in the mental development of children with congenital or acquired defects of the sensory, motor, intellectual and emotional spheres;

- theoretical analysis of domestic, foreign directions and methods of correctional and rehabilitation training;

- knowledge of applied aspects of stimulation of compensatory possibilities of psyche and development of personality of children;

- mastering the methods of organizing a humane social environment that promotes development of compensatory mechanisms of behaviour, as well as psychological and pedagogical principles of design and organization of situations of joint activities in the system “teacher-child-parents”;

- knowledge of methods of organizing a system of complex psychological, medical and pedagogical services (www.edu.ru/db/cgi-bin/portal/spe/list_search.plx?substr=022700; www.edu.ru/db/cgi-bin/portal/spe/list_search.plx?substr=031900).

A specialist in the field of special psychology must possess the following:

- the ability to conduct a psychological examination to determine the level of mental development, compliance with the age standards; methods of differential diagnosis to determine the type of deviations; ability to formulate a psychological conclusion;

- methods of counselling people with developmental disorders, their parents (guardians) and teachers on issues of education, development, life and professional self-determination;

- methods of psychoprophylactic work aimed at creating a favourable psychological climate in the educational and rehabilitation institution, family;

- skills and abilities to develop and implement correctional and educational programs; methods of psychological correction; knowledge of prevention and methods of correction of habits that are harmful to health, the means of protection against the adverse effects of the social environment;

- ways to provide psychological assistance in dangerous and emergency situations of natural, man-made and social origin;

- skills for organizing and conducting research work.

The specialist should be prepared to work in educational and medical institutions, as well as in social protection institutions of various types, which provide assistance to children and adults with developmental disorders: in psychological-medical-pedagogical commissions, psychological-medical-social centres, groups of short-term stay of mass kindergartens, in special preschool and school educational institutions of various types, in rehabilitation centres of health care and social protection system, in orphanages and boarding schools, psychoneurological boarding schools and clinics.

The leading types of professional activity of a special psychologist are:

1) diagnostic-analytical, expert – differential diagnostics to determine the type of disorders, to formulate a psychological conclusion;

2) consultative, psychoprophylactic – counselling of children and adults with developmental disorders, parents and teachers on issues of education, development, life and professional self-determination; conducting a psychological and pedagogical examination to determine the level of mental development, compliance with age norms; conducting psychoprophylactic work aimed at creating a favourable psychological climate in the educational institution, psychoprophylactic work with staff; providing psychological assistance to families; providing psychological assistance in dangerous and emergency situations of natural, man-made and social origin;

3) socio-pedagogical, educational – planning and conducting activities for socio-psychological prevention in the process of teaching and education, career guidance, assistance in socialization of students, implementation of personality-oriented approach to education and development of children; formation of spiritual, ethical values and moral beliefs in people with psychophysical disorders; application of modern psychological and pedagogical technologies;

4) correctional and developmental, rehabilitation – psychological support of the process of education and upbringing of children with developmental disorders; application of modern scientifically substantiated and most adequate methods of psycho-correctional work, in particular technical means of training and diagnostics, information and computer technologies;

5) cultural and educational – formation of general and psychological culture of participants in the educational process and the immediate social environment of children with mental and physical disabilities;

6) research, scientific-methodical – performance of scientific-methodical work, participation in the work of scientific-methodical associations; self-analysis and self-assessment in order to improve one's skills; development and implementation of correctional and educational programs;

7) organizational and managerial – ensuring protection of life and health of students during the educational process; maintaining school and classroom documentation; organization of control over the results of education; organization and holding of extracurricular activities, etc. (www.edu.ru/db/cgi-bin/portal/spe/list_search.plx?substr=022700; www.edu.ru/db/cgi-bin/portal/spe/list_search.plx?substr=031900).

The profession of special psychologist belongs to the general group of professions, which are determined by “person-person” orientation. Shadrikov (1982) identified the following general features for the professions of the system (P - P): orientation of an individual to the field of interpersonal relations, a high level of communication skills, the ability to empathize (empathy), the ability to adequately perceive and evaluate people; purity, clarity and expressiveness of speech; pronounced facial expression and behaviour, the ability to control oneself and influence others.

Klimov (2010) gave the most complete description of the subject of activity with such orientation in his systematic researches. Professions of this type require a creative mind, the ability to clearly imagine, to model the possible consequences of people's actions, a pronounced ability to predict, including empirical. There are also special requirements for self-regulation of this type of profession. It is necessary to constantly improve one's knowledge and skills, the need to monitor the changing processes of the social movement and reorganize in accordance with them.

Speech defects, slurred speech, isolation, low level of sociability, slowness, indifference to people, lack of signs of selfless interest in people, etc. are undesirable professional characteristics (Klimov, 2010).

An important quality of a psychologist is his personal and social maturity. In our opinion, personal maturity presupposes independent solution of one's own life problems, openness, tolerance and sincerity towards people. Social maturity provides an opportunity to help others solve their problems effectively.

Based on the research of Isaeva & Chebotarev (2001), we came to the conclusion that the personality of a specialist in the field of special psychology differs by an urgent need for social cognition. In this case, the interest in another person as an object of professional activity of the above specialists is not related to satisfaction of other needs, such as the need to

confirm their own personal significance and a sense of power (Nerubasska et al., 2020; Nerubasska & Maksymchuk, 2020; Sheremet et al., 2019).

The professional activity of a specialist in the field of special psychology is axiologically manifested in implementation of the humanistic approach to personality. Aminov & Molokanov (1992), Danylova (2004) and others drew attention to this. As Isaeva & Chebotarev (2001) point out, the humanistic orientation of professional practice-oriented activity presumes that specialists are willing to understand and be tolerant of another person, trying to be useful, to bring good.

A necessary prerequisite for activity in this area is the ability to empathize with another person. Development of empathy “as a moral quality” is closely related to the surrounding reality, and its psychological features are: reflection of condition of an individual; reflection of “objects and phenomena, on the basis of which emerge certain needs, goals and motives of a person who is in a certain emotional state”; active action “... undertaken by a subject experiencing a certain empathic feeling and in a certain way reflecting the objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality” (Krotenko, 2001, p. 158). Professionally important qualities are: observation, which is aimed at behavior, manifestations of the mental state of an individual; sensitivity, decency, helpfulness.

A comprehensive list of professional requirements for a special psychologist is given below. Thus, the effective solution in the future of various occupational and psychological problems largely depends on the availability and level of maturity of professionally important components of the personality of a special psychologist:

- professional and personal qualities, such as: reflexivity, empathy, adequacy and consistency of self-esteem, sensitivity, affiliation, altruism, tolerance, absence of chronic intra-personal conflicts;
- integrity of the “self-concept” of the specialist, which affects the content and context of corrective action;
- professionally important social-cognitive and communicative skills: listening to another person, establishing social contact, convincing another person, inspiring, etc.;
- professionally important qualities and properties of attention, perception, imagination, thinking (attentiveness, observation, ability to notice details in verbal and nonverbal behaviour; flexibility, plasticity and dynamism of thinking, ability to predict reactions and actions of a child; reflect on oneself and others, model the consequences works, etc.);
- psychophysical and mental qualities that allow to define the nervous system of a psychologist as quite stable, strong, stress-resistant, and,

at the same time, quite flexible and plastic, which causes high efficiency and self-regulation of personality, lack of tendency to mental arousal and rapid exhaustion;

– projective, acting, even directing (for example, in training or in group psychocorrection) and organizational skills that allow one to effectively implement game tools and psychotechnics, group tools of psycho-correctional, developmental and psychotherapeutic work.

The level of maturity of the above-mentioned psychological components of the personality of a specialist in the field of special psychology largely ensures productivity of professional activity and competence in solving psychological problems and providing qualified psychological counselling, the prerequisite for formation of which is professional orientation.

The review-critical analysis of the literature on the problem of personality orientation allowed us to consider professional orientation as a psychological readiness for the chosen professional activity, which is expressed in cognitive interest, needs, values, beliefs, worldview, professional ideas and professional intentions. Professional orientation acts as a basic construct that determines specifics of the profession of a psychologist and significantly affects his professional and personal success, manifesting itself in both stable personality traits and situational mental states associated with professional activities. This understanding of professional orientation is the basis for experimental research and identification of psychological features of the development of professional orientation of future special psychologists for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders.

Theoretical study of issues of personal and professional development of a psychologist during his studies at the university and the study of components of professional orientation for correctional support of children with psychophysical disorders allowed to put forward the basic assumption that professional orientation of a special psychologist has specific characteristics, associated with the peculiarities of this professional activity, is a major factor in the effective correctional support of this category of children and requires experimental research.

The main determinants of professional orientation for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders

Among the objectives of our study there is development of an adequate methodology for researching the professional orientation on

correctional support for children with mental and physical disorders to determine its psychological characteristics and levels of development, as well as studying its dynamics in the process of university training of future specialists in special psychology. To achieve this task, it is necessary to identify the main determinants of professional orientation of future special psychologists for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, the study of which will provide an opportunity to build an objective holistic picture of this process.

Scientific research of professionally oriented personal determinants of the psychologist's activity has traditionally been focused on the analysis of professionally important qualities, abilities and skills. Professional orientation is a subjective phenomenon, it is the result of professional self-determination of an individual, which can result in a positive, uncertain or negative attitude towards the future profession. When researching the professional orientation of students, it is necessary to first pay attention to the following parameters: motivation to choose the profession and the degree of satisfaction with it; steady interest in future professional activity; self-assessment of own compliance with the requirements of the chosen profession; realistic ideas about the future profession and the availability of professional plans, etc.

Defining the determinants of professional orientation of future special psychologists for correctional support of children with psychophysical disorders, we identified them based on the structural components of professional orientation: motivational-target, emotional-gnostic and regulatory.

Motivational and target component of the professional orientation of the future psychologist for correctional support of children with psychophysical development disorders reflects the dominant motives for choosing and mastering the profession, their stability; formation of humanistic orientation; semantic life orientations of the individual.

The emotional-gnostic component of the professional orientation of future psychologists on the correctional support of children with psychophysical disabilities is represented, in our opinion, ideas about future professional activity, its requirements for the personality of the specialist; attitude to the future profession and the process of mastering it; professional identification; empathy, tolerance, altruism and attraction; professional reflection.

The regulatory component of the professional orientation of future psychologists on the correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders determines formation and development of professional

self-esteem; professional self-preservation; professional forecasting and anticipation, as well as facilitation mechanisms and the sense of responsibility for the results of their own professional activities.

In studying the motivational-target component of the professional orientation of the future specialist in the field of psychology, we focused on the study of the dominant motives for choosing the profession; on formation of a humanistic orientation; on the meaningful life orientations of an individual.

At the present stage of development of society, the problem of conscious, balanced enrolling in a higher education establishment is relevant. Therefore, the motives for choosing a future profession, in our opinion, can serve as indicators of the level of professional orientation of future psychologists for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, which will affect effectiveness of both vocational training and further professional activity. According to Yaroshenko (1983), the motives for choosing a profession are reduced to professional interest, public duty and self-assessment of professional suitability.

Studying professional interests as determinants of choosing a profession, she came to the conclusion that all professional interests are divided into two groups: group A – direct professional interests, which include general-professional, professional-specific, situational and romantic; group B – indirect professional interests, specifically: professional-cognitive interest, interest in self-education, interest in prestige, interest in parallel opportunities, naive-selfish and unidentified interests.

Regarding public duty, Yaroshenko (1983) identified the following set of motives for choosing a profession – motives for duty, which are formed during the individual's awareness of one's own socially useful activities: responsibility for professional duties, striving for the highest level of professionalism, innovation in performance and organization of professional activity, general altruistic and civil aspirations.

Self-assessment of professional suitability was considered by the author as a relationship between the quality of self-esteem and the psychophysiological personality traits that students used to determine self-esteem (Yaroshenko, 1983).

The motives for choosing a profession are closely related to the motives for enrolment into a higher education establishment and characterize the attitude of students to the chosen professional activity. Shavir (1981, pp. 217-218) singled out five components in the structure of professional orientation, which can be considered motives for choosing a profession: 1) professional interests and inclinations – procedural motivation

of activity, which expresses the need for the specifics of this profession; 2) reflection of the peculiarities of the profession in the public consciousness – prestige, social significance; 3) personal needs that are relevant in connection with the profession – self-realisation, self-affirmation, material needs, personality traits, etc.; 4) features of self-awareness in interaction with the profession – belief in one’s suitability, mission, abilities, etc.; 5) interest in external, objectively insignificant attributes of the specialty. This takes into account “the content and depth of professional interest, taking into consideration its position in the system of motives for professional orientation”.

In the study of Gubaidullina (2000), the motives for choosing a higher education establishment are considered as one of the indicators of students’ professional orientation. She also found a mostly unmotivated choice of university in a large number of students, which was mostly based on the desire to obtain higher education.

The next problem of optimizing the educational and cognitive activities of students, which affects development of adequate and sustainable professional orientation, is the study of issues related to the meaningful orientations of the individual.

In our study, the above-mentioned orientations are well-known needs, which are often focused on in post-Soviet and Western psychology (Asmolov, 1983; Orlov, et al., 1981): Achievement, Cognizance, Dominance, Affiliation. We believe that these needs are decisive in the motivational-target component of professional orientation for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders because:

- the need to achieve implies the desire of the individual to improve the results of their own activities and is closely related to such personality traits as determination, perseverance, high adequate level of demands, efficiency, etc.;

- the cognizance need characterizes a person’s desire to expand experience and knowledge, to understand and systematize one’s own knowledge, erudition, curiosity, the desire to be competent (Orlov, 1981);

- affiliative tendencies of the individual are understood as the need of a person to establish, maintain and strengthen emotionally positive relationships with others, which are closely related to such concepts as tolerance, empathy (Zabrodin & Sosnovsky, 1989);

- domination is understood as the desire to govern, to influence other people in order to change their behaviour, attitudes, intentions, ideas, judgement; as the desire for organizational activities, leadership, etc.; but

with insufficiently developed organizational abilities, domination is transformed into a manipulative form of communication.

Maturity of humanistic orientation is viewed upon as an aptitude to integral sensitivity to the subjects, process and results of psychological activity (Aminov & Molokanov, 1992). Such well-known psychologists as Semichenko & Galus, (2003), Panok et al., (2016) emphasize that the main tool of psychological influence is the personality of a practical psychologist, the leading characteristic of which is the humanistic orientation, expressed through the perception of an individual as a unique value, through the ability to empathize and support. In dissertation research of Danylova (2004) humanistic orientation is presented as “a multicomponent structure, which includes: a high level of motivation to master the profession, which is dominated not only by cognitive but also altruistic, empathetic motives for working with people; willingness to cooperation and optimistic focus on the positive result of psychological influence; a balanced system of existential-humanistic values and value orientations; a high level of the ability to reflection and self-knowledge”. Humanistic orientation is especially important when working with children with mental and physical disorders, so we consider it an indicative determinant when considering the level of professional orientation to the correctional support of such children.

Examining the emotional and gnostic component of the professional orientation of future psychologists for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, represented by sensory and informational structures, we paid attention to the maturity and objectivity of the idea of future professional activity, its requirements to the personality of a specialist; on the attitude to the future profession and to the process of mastering it; identification with the subjects of the future professional activity; to the level of development of empathy, altruism and attraction.

In the context of professional orientation of students' personalities, an important role is played by the idea of future professional activity and a positive attitude to it, which is an important factor in increasing the students' success and efficiency of their future professional activity. One of the conditions for formation and development of adequate and sustainable professional orientation of future psychologists for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders is a preliminary development of their objective understanding of the professional activities of specialists in special psychology. Usually, a professional representation is understood as a set of certain information about the chosen profession and about the professional activity in general, which is owned by the subject (Lyubimova, 2002).

Most scholars (Lyubimova, 2002; Markova, 1996; Obnosov, 1998; Panok et al., 2016; Zeer, 2006) are convinced that the system of professional ideas is rather a complex structure, which includes semantic and emotional aspects. In studying the emotional and gnostic component of professional orientation for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, we are more interested in the emotional aspect of the system of professional ideas, i.e., students' attitudes to the psychological profession, to children with mental and physical disorders, to themselves as special psychologists.

Development of subjective professional ideas, which is not accompanied by their psychological and pedagogical correction, leads to formation of "narrow models of the future profession, hindering further professional growth" (Obnosov, 1998).

In the structure of professional orientation for psycho-correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, along with professional ideas, professional identity also plays an important role. Identity is a system of the most general ideas about oneself and one's place in the world. It also involves self-awareness as a professional. But professional self-determination is not reduced to a one-time choice, it begins long before the event, and lasts after it as long as continues further training and mastery of the profession. Azbel (2004) identifies four statuses of professional identity that reflect the stages of professional self-determination:

- uncertain professional identity: the choice of further way is not made, clear ideas about career are absent, but the person does not even set such a purpose;
- forced professional identity: an individual has formed ideas about their professional future, but they are forced from the outside (for example, from parents) and are not the result of an independent choice;
- moratorium (crisis of choice) of professional identity: an individual is aware of the problem of choosing a profession and is in the process of solving it, but the most appropriate option has not yet been determined;
- mature professional identity: professional plans are defined, which is the result of a conscious independent decision (Gladkaya, 2006).

The next and one of the obligatory determinants of professional orientation on corrective support of children with mental and physical disorders is empathy – the ability to respond emotionally, to empathize with another person. As noted by Krotenko (2001), empathy should be considered as a socio-psychological trait of an individual, which is a set of socio-psychological abilities. "Such abilities include: the ability to react emotionally to the experiences of another person and mentally transfer

oneself into the thoughts, feelings, and behaviour of another person; the ability to use ways of interacting that alleviate suffering of another person". Krotenko (2001) determined that in the optimal case, the development of empathy involves transition from compassion to empathy. Compassion is expressed in the emotional response to the grief or joy of another person that arises at the moment of passive contemplation of an empathogenic situation, while empathy is "the ability of a person not only to see suffering of another person in an empathogenic situation, but also to deeply understand their essence, undertake active action aimed at resolving the empathogenic situation".

Boyko (1996) draws attention to the accompanying characteristics of empathy. He believes that attitudes that promote or hinder empathy, respectively, facilitate or complicate the action of all empathy channels. The effectiveness of empathy is reduced if a person seeks to avoid personal contact, considers it inappropriate to show interest in another person, convinced oneself to be calm about the experiences and problems of others. Such attitudes sharply limit the range of emotional sensitivity and empathic perception.

The penetrating ability in empathy is regarded by Boyko (1996) as an important communicative trait of a person, which allows to create an atmosphere of openness, trust. Identification is another prerequisite for successful empathy. This is the ability to understand another person on the basis of empathy, putting oneself in the place of a partner. The basis of identification is lightness, mobility and flexibility of emotions, the ability to imitate (Raigorodsky, 2002).

As noted by Krotenko (2001), empathic feelings affect the volitional qualities of an individual. Being in an empathogenic situation directs the individual to conscious activity, purposefulness and orderliness of behaviour. Volitional regulation of the empathic response is determined by conditions in which it occurs.

Closely related to empathy altruism is "a rule of moral activity that recognizes as the duty of an individual to put the interests of other people and the common good above personal interests" (Meshcheryakova, Zinchenko, 2007), attraction is a special kind of social attitude to another person based on formation of a stable emotionally positive assessment of it; "... friendly type of relations between people, their sympathies for each other" (Meshcheryakova, Zinchenko, 2007) and congruence – "authenticity, openness, honesty ... it is a question of experiencing one's own feelings, of their openness to oneself and other people ... a special mode of effective

work of any facilitator (psychotherapist, consultant, teacher, parent)” (Meshcheryakova, Zinchenko, 2007).

The regulatory component of the professional orientation of future psychologists on the correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders was studied by us taking into account the level of maturity of professional self-esteem and professional prognosis. Let’s consider this issue in more detail.

Analysis of the psychological and pedagogical literature revealed that the system of professional ideas is rather a complex structure, which includes semantic and emotional aspects. When studying the regulatory component of professional orientation for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders, we were interested in the content aspect, which assumes that students have ideas about features of the chosen profession (the image of the profession) and professionally significant qualities of the specialist (the image of the professional).

The success of the specialist is determined not only by the level of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, but also the degree of maturity of professionally important personal qualities. The process of forming the image of a professional involves development of students’ ideas about professionally important qualities of a specialist, which are the basis for assessing their own compliance with the requirements of the chosen profession, i.e., for development of professional self-esteem.

A sufficiently high level of knowledge about the objective content, conditions and prospects of future professional activity, as well as the necessary professional qualities is an important condition for both the validity of choosing a profession and creative mastery of future specialty and enjoyment of its implementation.

In our opinion, the ability to make professional predictions is an equally important determinant of professional orientation for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders. Professional prediction provides an opportunity to reliably foresee the results of their own activities and actions, the activities of other people, some events, on the basis of which one can build tactics of current behaviour, choose adequate methods of action, etc. (Regush, 1997). Also, professional prediction involves planning of the way to achieve professional goals with definition of the main stages, ways and means, possible obstacles and ways to overcome them; development of professionally important qualities and success in mastering professional activity; plays an important role in assessing the completion of professional development, in the ability to identify and adjust the compliance of professional activities in accordance with the

requirements of the specialty, etc. (Saraeva, 2003). Slyusareva (2007) singled out a practical component in the structure of a special psychologist's readiness for psychocorrectional work with children, closely linking it with analytical, design, reflective and prognostic skills, which, in our opinion, reflect an individual's ability to build a plan of professional self-actualization.

Conclusions

It is found that the main determinants of professional orientation for correctional support of children with mental and physical disorders are: dominant motives for choosing and mastering the profession; maturity of humanistic orientation; meaningful life orientations of the individual, maturity and objectivity of ideas about future professional activity, its requirements for the personality of a specialist; positive attitude to the future profession and to the process of mastering it; identification with the subjects of future professional activity; high level of development of empathy, altruism and attraction; maturity of an adequate professional self-assessment and professional prediction.

Based on this, the psychological features of the professional orientation of future psychologists for correctional support, which determine the highest level of its maturity, should be considered a clear humanistic orientation, mature professional motives for the public benefit of their own activities; well-developed altruistic tendencies, empathy in its active form, high level of communicative tolerance, real optimism; adequate professional self-esteem, which is formed on the basis of the existing objective image of the profession and personality of the specialist; high level of self-control and self-regulation, which are reflected in increased stress resistance and responsibility for one's own professional activities.

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